

Studies in the Protective Action of Colloids. Part II.

BY SHRIDHAR SARVOTTAM JOSHI AND A. JOGA RAO.

In Part I of this series (p. 237) a fixed quantity of the arsenious sulphide sol, protected by varying concentrations of a number of protecting agents, was coagulated by different electrolytes. It was found that the curves relating the amount of ionic adsorption with the corresponding concentration of the protector showed sharp discontinuities, which were attributed to the formation of adsorption complexes with specific adsorptive capacities. The following experiments were carried out in order to investigate if the above discontinuities were accompanied by a like change in two of the physical properties of the system, *viz.*, the viscosity and the turbidity, and their variation due to 'ageing'. The adsorption by the colloid of the protector itself also appeared to be a possible factor, and has been studied in the case of sodium oleate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

25 C. c. of the arsenious sulphide sol were taken into each of a number of well cleaned 100 c. c. flasks. Into one of these, 25 c. c. of distilled water were added; in the rest the same volume of gelatine solutions of increasing concentrations (denoted by p in Tables I—IV), was added. The mixtures were then shaken, and their viscosities and turbidities determined. These measurements were again taken after the the mixtures were allowed to stand (screened from light) for 30 hours.

The viscosity was measured by the method due to Scarpa (*Gazzetta*, 1920, 40, 271; *cf.* also, Farrow, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347). It consists in measuring the time of rise, t_1 and of fall, t_2 for a certain volume of the liquid against a constant reduced pressure, and under a certain hydrostatic pressure of the liquid itself, respectively. The viscosity, η , is then given by,

$$\eta = \frac{k.t_1.t_2}{t_1 + t_2}$$

where k is a constant for the instrument used and can be evaluated by measuring t_1 and t_2 for a liquid whose viscosity is known, *e.g.*, water. The colloid solutions were allowed to attain the desired temperature by immersion in a thermostat for about half an hour. The thermostat temperature was kept constant within 0.05° . In Tables I—IV, p denotes the concentration of the gelatine solution; it was used as a protector in experiments to which Tables II, III, and IV refer. Table I gives η , for different values of p , for gelatine solutions only. Table II shows the viscosities of the gelatine-protected sols observed immediately after the addition of the protecting agent, for different values of p . Data in Tables III and IV refer to two independent series of experiments in which η was observed 30 hours after mixing the gelatine solution with the colloid.

Turbidity was determined by means of an instrument of a Nephelometer type. It consists essentially of two tubes to hold the liquids to be examined, which are illuminated from below. The depths of the liquids as shown by separate indicators can be varied by a rack and pinion arrangement, and the beams emerging from the liquid columns matched by viewing through the eyepieces fitted on the tubes. The left hand tube was always filled with the arsenious sulphide sol diluted with an equal volume of water, the indicator being kept at a certain height. The other tube was filled with the liquid to be examined for turbidity. The height of the latter, as shown by the indicator, is varied till the beams emerging from the two tubes just matched. This measurement was repeated with at least two different heights of the indicator in the standard liquid. The difference between the two heights gave a measure of the turbidity relative to that of the liquid taken as the standard. Table V and curves 1 and 2, Fig. 2, give the results of these measurements immediately after the sol was mixed with gelatine solutions of varying concentrations. Turbidities were determined for the same mixtures after 24 hours, and the results obtained shown in Table VI, and by curves 3, 4 and 5 in Fig. 2.

Experiments were next made in order to obtain some idea of the adsorption by the colloid of the protecting substance used, *viz.*, sodium oleate. Surface tensions of differently concentrated solutions of sodium oleate were measured by means of a stalagmometer. The solutions were so dilute that the difference of their densities from that of water was found to be negligible. Surface tensions have been indicated therefore only by the drop numbers. The results are shown

by the curve 6 in Fig. 3. Mixtures were next prepared in which a constant volume of the sol was protected by an equal volume of sodium oleate solution of different concentrations. The mixtures were allowed to stand for 24 hours, and their drop numbers determined. These are shown under D in Table VII. a and $a/2$ refer respectively to sodium oleate concentrations before and after mixing. Sodium oleate concentrations corresponding to the drop numbers, D , observed for the mixed solutions were next read off from curve 6 in Fig. 3 and are quoted under b in Table VII. $(a/2 - b)$ was taken as a measure of the amount of sodium oleate removed from water due to its adsorption by the colloid. Curve 7 in Fig. 3 relates the amount of the above adsorption with the concentration of the protector.

TABLE I.

Pure gelatine solutions.

P.	t_1 .	t_2 .	η .	t_1 .	t_2 .	η .	t_1 .	t_2 .	η .	t_1 .	t_2 .	η .	t_1 .	t_2 .	η .					
0·000	6'	42·8	11'	37·4	0·894	6'	50·4	11'	44·8	0·908	6'	51·4	11'	34·8	0·905	6'	50·4	11'	36·0	0·910
0·001	6	45·0	11	39·6	0·902	6'	54·6	11	45·8	0·914	6	52·4	11	47·4	0·912	6	50·8	11	47·6	0·915
0·003	6	47·4	11	46·0	0·904	6'	56·0	11	50·4	0·918	6	52·2	11	48·5	0·912	6	53·8	11	58·5	0·919
0·006	6	58·4	11	53·6	0·937	6'	58·8	11	56·6	0·925	6	55·8	12	0·0	0·922	7	25·0	11	40·8	0·928
0·010	7	11·4	11	56·0	0·942	6'	59·0	12	4·0	0·929	6	53·6	11	55·4	0·918	6	41·2	11	51·2	0·908
0·015	7	15·2	12	22·8	0·961	6'	59·0	12	12·8	0·934	6	45·0	11	56·8	0·908	6	40·0	11	46·2	0·903
0·020	7	20·0	12	38·3	0·974	7'	0	12	15·0	0·936	6	46·0	12	0·0	0·909	6	45·0	11	52·5	0·909
0·030	7	37·4	13	4·4	1·011	7'	1·0	12	15·2	0·937	6	48·8	12	2·0	0·914	6	48·0	11	46·6	0·910
0·040	7	55·0	13	41·6	1·054	7'	7·0	12	25·0	0·950	6	55·0	12	3·0	0·923	6	50·0	11	47·4	0·914
0·050	8	11·4	14	16·8	1·093	7'	9·4	12	40·0	0·950	6	54·0	12	2·0	0·921

TABLE II.

Colloid + gelatine solutions.
 η Observed soon after
mixing.

TABLE III.

Colloid + gelatine solutions. η Observed 30 hours
after mixing.

TABLE IV.

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TABLE V.

Immediately after mixing.

TABLE VI.

After 24 hours.

No.	Percentage of gelatine.	Left height in cm.	Right height in cm.	Relative turbidity.	Left height in cm.	Right height in cm.	Relative turbidity.
1	0.000	20	20	0	10	10	0
	„	30	30	0	20	20	0
	„	30	30	0	30	30	0
2	0.001	20	19	1	10	7	3
	„	„	„	„	20	16.5	3.5
	„	„	„	„	30	22	8
3	0.003				10	6	4
	„	20	15	5	20	12.5	7.5
	„	30	20	10	30	16	14
4	0.006				10	5	5
	„	20	12	8	20	8	12
	„	30	16	14	30	12	18
5	0.010				10	4	6
	„	20	8	12	20	5.5	14.5
	„	30	10.5	19.5	30	8	22
6	0.015				10	2.5	7.5
	„	20	6	14	20	4.5	15.5
	„	30	7	23	30	5.5	24.5
7	0.020				10	2	∞
	„	20	4.5	15.5	20	3.5	16.5
	„	30	6.0	24	30	5	25
8	0.030				10	2	8
	„	20	4.5	15.5	20	3.5	16.5
	„	30	5.5	24.5	30	5	25
9	0.040				10	1.5	8.5
	„	20	3.5	16.5	20	2.5	17.5
	„	30	4.5	25.5	30	3.5	26.5
10	0.050				10	1	9
	„	20	3	17	20	2.5	17.5
	„	30		26	30	3.5	26.5

TABLE VII.

<i>a.</i>	<i>a/2.</i>	<i>D.</i>	<i>b.</i>	$\frac{a}{2} - b.$
0.05	0.025	163	0.0155	0.0095
0.10	0.050	177	0.0165	0.0335
0.20	0.100	254	0.0180	0.0820
0.25	0.125	272	0.0200	0.1050
0.30	0.150	300	0.0263	0.1237
0.40	0.200	335	0.0350	0.1650

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

Turbidity observed soon after mixing. Curves 1 and 2 with the standard liquid at heights of 20 and 30 cm. respectively.

Turbidity observed 24 hours after mixing. Curves 3-5 with standard liquid at heights of 10, 20 and 30 cm. respectively.

FIG. 3.

DISCUSSION.

It is seen from curve 1, Fig. 1, that, η , the viscosity of gelatine solutions increases practically linearly by increasing p , its concentration. Similar results have been observed by Davis and Oakes, (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1526; *ibid.*, 1922, **44**, 464). The η - p relation is also a simple one for mixture of gelatine solutions with the colloid, η being determined soon after mixing (*cf.* curve 2, Fig. 1). Marked discontinuities, similar to those observed previously (Part I) in ionic adsorption-protector concentration curves, appeared when the protected sols were allowed to stand for a period of about 30 hours (curves 3 and 4). These two sets of results although not identical are sufficiently similar to show that the positions of discontinuity are more than mere accidental breaks due to experimental error. Indeed a lack of complete reproducibility of results within a given time period is well known in colloidal systems, and is to be attributed to the heterogeneity of the solutions, and the marked dependence of their properties on the manner of their preparation, especially in the case of lyophiles, although the same quantities of the materials are used. We are inclined, therefore, to consider the above discontinuities as indicative of (i) some kind of interaction between the protector and the colloid, (ii) some sudden changes in the nature and the size of particles of the dispersed phase, or (iii) what is more likely, due to the combined effect of (i) and (ii). Possibly these changes are amongst the main factors in the so-called 'ageing' phenomena, in which a time variation of some of the properties of colloids, notably of the viscosity, is observed. In this connection it is interesting to point out that the above changes in viscosity produced within only 30 hours are markedly greater than those found usually in the 'ageing' of simple sols, and might, therefore, be distinctive of only the protected systems.

It is important to note that the turbidity measurements show only a continuous increase with the concentration of the protector in every case. While the explanation of this result requires more detailed experimental work on protected sols, it may be perhaps permissible to point out one general result noted incidentally in the course of studies of the coagulation processes and using different methods of measuring the degree of coagulation which has been in progress for some time in these laboratories, that a given change in a colloid system does not reveal itself equally markedly in all its properties (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 11, 337; *ibid.*, 1932, **9**, 157).

By comparing curves 4 and 5 with 1 and 2 in Fig. 2, it is seen that turbidity diminishes with ageing, and that this diminution is more appreciable at low proportions of the protector.

It is well known that one of the chief difficulties of interpreting results for protected systems in general, has been that no accurate method is available for the estimation of the adsorption of the protector. We have determined this for sodium oleate on the assumption that the difference in the surface tension of its solution when pure, and when mixed with the colloid is due entirely to its adsorption by the colloid ($\frac{a}{2} - b$, in Table VII). This is supported by the fact that the surface tension of the colloid solution used in the above experiments differed but little from that of pure water. The possible ascribability of the observed change of surface tension to alterations in the nature of the colloid particles in the system, besides that due to the factor assumed above, must be regarded as an open question. Our main assumption would appear, however, to be confirmed by the significant result (*cf.* curve 7, Fig. 3) that the amount of sodium oleate adsorbed increases practically linearly as its concentration is increased.

THE CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY,
BENARES.

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